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Vol. XIX

Eds.

Subir Dhar, Bryan Reynolds, Sheila T. Cavanagh, Papia Mitra

A

Special Publication of
The Shakespeare Society of Eastern India

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**Subir Kumar Dhar
Bryan Reynolds
Sheila T. Cavanagh
Papia Mitra**

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Phone: (033) 2466 2688 / 98304 05624 / 9748726895.

E.mail: tapu_biswas@yahoo.com, drtapubiswas@gmail.com

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Shakespeare Society of Eastern India & Tagore-Gandhi Institute
mourns the passing away of

Amitava Roy
(1947–2024)

Professor Emeritus, Bankura University,
Former Shakespeare Professor & Head, Department of English,
Rabindra Bharati University,
Former Director, Shakespeare Centre for Advanced Research,
Rabindra Bharati University,
Executive President, Shakespeare Society of Eastern India,
Globally Renowned Theatre Director and Actor.
You left thousands of students and admirers disconsolate
on 12th April, 2024
Farewell and Rest in Peace after your journey's end.

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**Intercultural performance from the late 1990s in India -
A study of Dance - Theatre encounters in *Bharangam***

B. Shrikant Nandkumar

Abstract

The end of the 20th century can be considered the most significant in the history of Indian theatre when the National School of Drama first organized the Bharat Ranga Mahotsav (BRM) in 1999. The influence of Western Performance Art on Indian Theatre is evident in the way that it helped shape the vision of young Indian directors and choreographers. They were actively involved in bringing out ethnic influences while placing them in the new modes of Western dynamic movement, thus creating new genres that intensified the beauty of Indian performing arts. BRM has become one of the most vital areas where one can express oneself and experiment – a dance-theatre hybrid. These productions best characterize the relationship between dance and theater since both have their roots in the early performance arts. This interconnectivity is evident in BRM's featured works wherein all these elements have been integrated into the composition. Therefore, an even greater emphasis is placed on exploring the large number of cross-cultural performances in BRM's dance-theatre productions. While these works incorporate features such as light, automation, and mechanical effects that are performed during the show, they give a new perspective and dimension for the view of the Indian audiences. Such directors and choreographers also show that conventional classical Indian and traditional dance themes can be depicted experimentally by borrowing from yoga, martial arts, and even contemporary dance. It liberates directors and choreographers to go out and think beyond the norms, hence seeing the stage as a platform for creating works that blend the field of dance and

theater and create new languages of movement and acting. In further advancement of the theatre in India, one will find that this aspect of the dance-drama combination will remain a constant. Thus, by encouraging these cultural interchanges, the BRM plays a crucial role in the development of Indian performance arts.

Keywords: Intercultural Performance, Bharat Ranga Mahotsav, Dance-Theatre, Indian Theatre, Traditional and Contemporary Dance, Choreographic Integration, Dance-Drama Fusion, Performance Practice

Introduction

It was in the late 1990s that a new era of Indian theatre was envisioned with the coming up of the Bharat Ranga Mahotsav. National School of Drama (NSD) spearheaded BRM- an annual international theatre festival in 1999. It was in 1991 that India emerged as one of the global villages by opting for a liberalization policy. Globalization aligns more Western culture with Indian performance, especially in live art, dance and theatre in particular. Western influences have brought an impact on the vision of the young directors and the choreographers of the time. Sunil Kothari writes, "The uniqueness of this panorama of new directions in Indian Dance lies in the "voice" of the creators/dancers and choreographers" (Kothari, 2003). The same stands true for the theatre directors as well. The duality maintained by them lies in the choices they made, either by looking into the ethnic traditions or incorporating the movement dynamics of the West. While taking the inspiration and the influences of the West, creative directors of the theatre and dance looked deep into their respective cultural roots. As a result, new genres of these forms have emerged, enhancing India's performance ethos. For example, the incorporation of allied forms, like folk and traditional theatre, yoga, native martial arts, and Western modern dance techniques were practiced. At this backdrop, Bharat Ranga Mahotsav has become the platform for experimentation, innovation, and creation. The productions that were staged in this festival became the canvas of both the Theatre of Roots¹ and the genres that emerged later in the Indian theatre. These productions stood as ideal illustrations of the coming together of dance and theatre elements.

Some of the plays that were showcased in BRM enabled the study of details of the polarities, overlapping, and similitudes of the allied arts of dance and theatre. This outlook evidently brings forth dance and theatre as two sides of the same coin. In fact, when examining the evolution of dance and theatre² it is obvious that these two arts emerged as a united one and later travelled independently in building up their respective identities. The interaction of dance drama has been part of the human civilization world over. In the process of their individual growth, they walked on the paths of improving on body dynamics and verbal dynamics respectively. The interaction and integration of these two arts of performance have been revisited through the works of the directors who were featured in BRM. The role of dance and drama in Indian theatre plays was visible through the directorial skills, choreographic displays, and production environment of the productions of the nineties.

The common elements shared by the classical dance forms of India and Indian Theatre can be enlisted as the Chaturvidaabhinaya³ mentioned by Bharata.⁴ Both the dance and drama exist on the fundamental components of the chaturvidaabhinaya. The primary purpose of Natya⁵ and Nritya⁶ is to narrate a story. The classical Indian dances like Bharatanatyam, Kathakali, Odissi, Kathak, Manipuri, Sattriya, Kuchipudi, and Mohiniattam are all arts of storytelling and hence hold an element of dramatization in them. In fact, Kuchipudi and Kathakali are dance-theatre forms.

The performance genres of the nineties have branched out as critical overlapping of arts that reflected body culture dynamics. A fusion of dance and yoga, dance and martial arts, dance and theatre, theatre and martial arts-based dance forms, theatre and modern dance of the West, and many similar permutations and combinations have flown swiftly. This period documented the conscious efforts to narrow down the gap between vibrant dance works and the contemporary theatre, resulting in productions, which were more challenging and cutting across different genres, such as Physical Theatre, and experimental productions by directors like Maya Krishna Rao⁷ in various Bharat Ranga Mahotsav.

The Bharat Ranga Mahotsav, since its initiation, has contributed greatly in creating such intercultural meetings. As a platform for various forms of theatrical performances, the festival has facilitated directors and choreographers to try out new ideas within the form and content, therefore, enhancing the quality of the theatre in India.

Analysis of Selected Productions

Data from the National School of Drama's archive was obtained and subsequently analyzed. 72 productions were selected based on their presentation styles and different parameters such as BRM Organizing Year, Name of The Play, Playwright, Director, Language, Director Details, Available Source, Dance-drama Production, Is Director Trained Dancer/choreographer, Dance-drama/choreography Used, Directors Dance Training Background. This data analysis holds definite findings about the alteration Like the Bharat Ranga Mahotsav, it has played an essential part in such types of creative arts, although it is a theatrical show. Therefore, the incorporation of body movement in theatre is a creative aspect that can transform the views of the traditional form.

A total of 1844 productions were watched and analyzed by reading news articles and evidences available online. Data spanning over Twenty-Five years (1999-2023) regarding Bharat Ranga Mahotsav (BRM) indicates that there was a total of Twenty-Two Annual BRM organized. NSD hosted the International Theatre Olympics 2018, where BRM merged into the international Theatre Festival. In the wake of the COVID-19 Pandemic, BRM in 2021 and 2022 were not organized. In all twenty-five years, the Total number of performed productions were 1844, of which 1763 were general theatre productions, and 72 were Dance-Drama or Dance-Theatre staged in various places in India during the festival. A high number of dance theatres were staged during the Theatre Olympics, and various artists across the globe participated in it.

BRM DANCE-DRAMA PRODUCTION STATISTIC (1999-2023)				
SR. NO.	BRM YEAR	NO. OF GENERAL PRODUCTION	NO. OF DANCE-DRAMA PRODUCTION	TOTAL
1	1999	56	0	56
2	2000	81	1	82
3	2001	74	1	75
4	2002	135	1	136
5	2003	81	1	82
6	2004	72	2	74
7	2005	55	2	57
8	2006	58	2	60
9	2007	30	7	37
10	2008	70	2	72
11	2009	60	1	61
12	2010	74	1	75
13	2011	77	4	81
14	2012	95	4	99
15	2013	82	3	85
16	2014	71	4	75
17	2015	80	2	82
18	2016	75	5	80
19	2017	70	3	82
20	(THEATRE OLYMPICS) 2018	143	17	160
21	2019	84	2	86
22	2020	61	5	66
23	(NOT ORGANIZED) 2021	0	0	0
24	(NOT ORGANIZED) 2022	0	0	0
25	2023	79	2	81
-	YEARS OF BRM	TOTAL NO. OF GENERAL PRODUCTIONS	TOTAL NO. OF DANCE-DRAMA PRODUCTIONS	TOTAL OF ALL PRODUCTIONS
-	22	1763	72	1844
-	INPERCENTAGE-	95.6	3.9	99.5

Table 1: BRM Dance-Drama/Dance-Theatre Production Statistic (1999-2023)

Graph of Dance-Theatre

Below is the data atglance in the graph. This data indicates the participation and performance of dance-theatre/dance-drama compared to general production in every Bharat Ranga Mahotsav.

Figure 1:BRM Production Statistic (1999-2004)

Figure 2:BRM Production Statistic (2005-2010)

Figure 3: BRM Production Statistic (2011-2016)

Figure 4: BRM Production Statistic (2017-2023)

The Dance-Theatre of *Bharangam*

The table below indicates the total dance-theatre/Dance-Drama productions staged during the twenty-five years of BRM and the Name of the Play, its Director, and Dance-Drama/Choreography used in respective productions. Comparing dance-drama productions from different years allows us to analyse the variety and experiments in

Indian theatre. This analysis focuses on the directorial aspects, choreographic arcs, and thematic emphases of these performances, demonstrating how dance-drama has developed and affected the Indian stage.

BRM - DANCE-DRAMA PRODUCTIONS & DETAILS				
SR. NO.	BRM YEAR	NAME OF THE PLAY	DIRECTOR	DANCE-DRAMA/CHOREOGRAPHY USED
1	2023	DAKSHAYAJNA (YAKSHAGANA)	KEREMANE SHIVANANDA HEGDE	Yakshagana, Folk Dance Movements
2	2023	SILENCE	SOMA GIRI	Bharatanatyam, Contemporary Dance Movements
3	2020	KARIMKUTTY	KAVALAM NARAYANA PANIKKAR	Traditional Indian Dance Movements
4	2020	A HUMAN ENDEAVOUR	SHILPIKA BORDOLOI	Contemporary Movements, Traditional Indian Dance Inspired
5	2020	LOOSE WOMAN	MAYA K. RAO	Contemporary Movements, Slow Body Movements
6	2020	KUMARI AND THE BEAST	KAVITA SRINIVASAN	Contemporary Body Movements
7	2020	LIVE NUKES!	KEVIN DUVALL / TAYLOR BREWERTON	Physical Theatre Movements, Contemporary Body Twist
8	2019	MOIMONSINGHA GE ITIKA	GOUTAM	Yes, Folk Dance Movements
9	2019	PAANCHALI LAASYA RANGA	B. JAYASHREE	Yes, Bharatanatyam and Folk Movements
10	2018	ALMOST ALIVE	SEBINE MOLENAAR	Dance-Drama (Physical Theater)
11	2018	BHAANAKA	PIYAL BHATTACHARYA	Dance-Drama (Indian Classical Dance Movements)
12	2018	BHINNA VINYASA	JAYACHANDRAN PALAZHY	Dance-Drama (Contemporary Movements)
13	2018	BUDDHA: NOT FOR SALVATION	DHIRENDRA MOHAN	Dance-Drama (Mixed and Folk)
14	2018	CROSSINGS: EXPLORING THE FACETS OF LADY MACBETH	VIKRAM IYENGAR	Dance-Drama (Indian Classical Dance Movements)

B. S. Nandkumar: Dance - Theatre encounters in Bharangam

15	2018	LAAVNI: FOLK	VAISHALI	LAVANI (FOLK)
16	2018	MADE IN ILVA	ANNA DORA DORNO	CONTEMPORARY
17	2018	MAYUR BHANJ CHHAU: FOLK	SADASHIV PRADHAN	CHHAU (FOLK)
18	2018	NERVES	SURJIT NONGMEIKAPAM	CONTEMPORARY
19	2018	NATIR PUJA	SUTAPA AWON PRADHAN	Bharatanatyam, Mayurbhanja Chhau and Contemporary Body Movement
20	2018	PYRAMUS & THISBY	JEHAN ALOYSIUS	Creative and Traditional
21	2018	RAI KRISHNA PADABALI	SUKALYAN BHATTACHARYA	Creative and Traditional
22	2018	THE RESTAURANT OF MANY ORDERS	HIROSHI KOIKE	Slow Movement (To deepen the awareness of one's "body", as per Hiroshi Koike)
23	2018	ROMEO & JULIET	BIRJU MAHARAJ	Kathak and Creative Choreography
24	2018	SAKURA	KEIIN YOSHIMURA	Kamigata-Mai (Traditional Japanese Dance)
25	2018	THE TRANSPARENT TRAP	SHRIKANT BHIDE	Physical theatre, Contemporary
26	2018	VITHAL TUKAYACHA	RAMDAS V PAWAR	Bharatanatyam
27	2017	ANAND RAGHUNANDAN	SANJAY UPADHYAY	Bharatanatyam, Indian Traditional Dance Movements
28	2017	CHITRA: A DANCE DRAMA	DR. SHRIPAD BHAT	Bharatanatyam, Indian Traditional Dance Movements
29	2017	RAM KI SHAKTI PUJA	VYOMKESH SHUKLA	Indian Traditional Dance Movements
30	2016	AJILAMU	SUK BAHADUR	AJIMALU RITUAL DANCE: Ajilamu is a ritualistic dance form of indigenous tribes of Arunachal Pradesh. The Shertukpen and Monpa Buddhist tribes perform Ajilamu on the occasion of their local festivals and life-cycle ceremonies.
31	2016	RAMAYANA	SHANTI BARDHAN	Various Indian Traditional Dance Movements
32	2016	SARAKELA CHAU	NILAY KUMAR SAHU	Saraikele Chhau, (Mask)

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33	2016	STRATA 2	MARIA DONATA D'URSO	Contemporary Dance, Slow Body Movements
34	2016	TRANSPARENT TRAP	SHRIKANT BHIDE	Contemporary Dance, Physical Theatre
35	2015	THE THINGS YOU SAID VIVIEN WOOD YOU NEVER SAID BEFORE YOU	VIVIEN WOOD	Physical Theatre, Contemporary Movement
36	2015	OTHELLO: KATHAKALI	SADANAM PV BALAKRISHNAN	Kathakali
37	2014	PURUSHASUKTA	JOSEPH JOHN	Indian Traditional Dance Movements, Chhau, Kalaripayattu
38	2014	WOMEN WHO DIDN'T WANT TO COME DOWN TO EARTH	GABRIELLE NEUHAUS	Physical Theatre, Contemporary Slow Dance Movements
39	2014	THOSE WHO COULD NOT HEAR THE MUSIC	VIKRAM IYENGAR	Contemporary Dance Movements
40	2014	UTSUSHI	USHIO AMAGATSU	Butoh, Contemporary Dance Movements
41	2013	ANVESHAN	SANGEETA SHARMA	Contemporary Dance, Movements Inspired by Indian Traditional Dance
42	2013	HANUMAN RAMAYANA & NIDRAVATWAM	NIMMY RAPHEL	Combination of traditional Indian Mohiniattam, Kuchipudi, traditional martial dances and contemporary body dance
43	2013	PARIKARMA	SHOBHA DEEPAK SINGH	Contemporary Dance, Movements Inspired by Indian Traditional Dance
44	2012	DRAVYA KAYA	NAVTEJ JOHAR	Contemporary Dance, Movements Inspired by Indian Traditional Dance
45	2012	THE GAME OF DICE: BASED ON AN EPISODE FROM THE MAHABHARATA	SANTOSH NAIR	Contemporary Dance, Movements Inspired by Indian Traditional Dance
46	2012	JALAM	MADHU GOPINATH & VAKKOM SAJEEV	Contemporary Dance, Various Movements by Indian Traditional Dance
47	2012	VISARJAN	SANGEETA SHARMA	Contemporary Dance, Movements Inspired by Indian Traditional Dance
48	2011	GREY IS ALSO A COLOUR	NAVTEJ JOHAR	Contemporary Dance, Movements Inspired by Indian Traditional Dance
49	2011	INHABITED GEOMETRY	MANDEEP RAIKHY	Contemporary Dance and Physical Theatre Movements

B. S. Nandkumar: Dance - Theatre encounters in Bharangam

50	2011	SURPRISED BODY PROJECT	FRANCESCO SCAVETTA	Contemporary Dance
51	2011	SWEET SORROW	PREETHI ATHREYA	Contemporary Dance with Indian Costume- Saree
52	2010	TILT	ANUSHA LALL	Yoga and Indian Martial Arts Movements
53	2009	PAINTED WORLD: THE BLACK LIGHT THEATER	THEODOR HOIDEKR	Contemporary Dance, Slow Body Movement, Light, Props Usage
54	2008	PAST IS SIMULATION: THE LADIES OF THE SEA VS NORA AND OTHER STORIES	MONICA EMILIE HERSTAD	Contemporary Dance, Ballet Motivated Body Movements
55	2008	THREE SISTERS	HIROSHI KOIKE	Contemporary Dance, Slow and Sudden Fast Body Movements
56	2007	BEHATI GANGA	SANGEETA SHARMA	Contemporary Dance, Movements Inspired by Indian Martial Arts
57	2007	KAIKEYEE	GEETA CHANDRAN & RASHID ANSARI	Bharatanatyam, Movements Inspired by Yoga, Indian Traditional Dance, Contemporary Dance (Performed by Geeta Chandran)
58	2007	KANNAPPAR KURAVANJI	RUKMANI DEVI ARUNDALE	Bharatanatyam, Movements Inspired Indian Traditional, Folk Dance, Dramatisation
59	2007	KHOL DO	MAYA KRISHNA RAO	Contemporary Dance, Slow Dance Movements with Abhinaya, Expressions
60	2007	MUKHANTAR, CONFERENCE	NARENDRA SHARMA	Contemporary Dance, Movements Inspired by Indian Folk Dances
61	2007	PAPERDOLL	PADMINI CHETTUR	Contemporary Dance, Slow Body Movements
62	2007	SEVERAL WITTY OBSERVATIONS	LESZEK BZDYL	Contemporary Dance
63	2006	ANTIM ADHYAY AND FLYING CRANES	NARENDRA SHARMA	Contemporary Dance, Movements Inspired by Indian Folk Dances
64	2006	OTHELLO	SADANAM P.V. BALAKRISHNAN	Kathakali
65	2005	AMMA	PROBIR GUHA	Contemporary Dance Movements
66	2005	HASYA CHUDAMANI	ROBIN DAS	Kathak and Contemporary Movements

67	2004	SOUND OF SILENCE	MADHU GOPINATH & VIKROM SANJEEV	Contemporary and Creative Dance Movements Inspired by Various Indian Dance Traditions
68	2004	VENUS PARTY	SINEENADH KEITPRAPAI	Physical Theatre and Contemporary Dance Movements.
69	2003	INVISIBLEST (UNSICHTBARST)(SOLO)	ANNA HUBER	Contemporary Dance and Physical Theatre Movements, Slow Body Movements
70	2002	DEEP FRIED JAM (SOLO)	MAYA KRISHNA RAO	Contemporary Dance, Slow Dance Movements with Vachika Abhinaya, Expressions, Technicality usage- Live Video Projection of her body movements.
71	2001	GOKUL NIRGAMANA	B.V. KARANTH	Although It a musical play cum dance-drama; Individual, supportive character movements based on folk, household and traditional dance. Such as Gopika, Radha, Krishna, and other villagers and characters.
72	2000	SOLO IN CONTEMPORARY DANCE	BHARAT SHARMA	No details found/As the title suggests, it is Indian Contemporary Dance

Table 2:BRM Dance-Drama/Dance-Theatre Production Details (1999-2023)

Directorial Approaches

The directors of these productions have sought to integrate dance with drama using different strategies, each with a different vision and aesthetics. For example, in the piece “Dakshayajna” (2023), Keremane Shivananda Hegde uses Yakshagana, a popular folk dance and stage acting, to enhance the performance and convey a rich culture. The employment of Yakshagana form by the director Hegde is unique because it underscores the mythological aspect of the story; at the same time, it is relevant to the modern-day world. The cultural essence of Yakshagana, which includes the vibrant costumes, the coordination in the movements, and the generosity in the gestures in the acting, is apparent, and at the same time, Hegde has demonstrated a balance

between tradition and the contemporary. Keremane Shridhara Hegde, a family member of Yakshagana Training Center at Gokarna, Karnataka, elaborates more about the center's training and the actor's preparation for the stage. During his visit in the Department of Dance, University of Hyderabad on October 25, 2022, in private communication, He says that, "Before the abhinaya, the dance part of the play and understanding the beats of a live orchestra is necessary for individual artists of Yakshagana" (Hegde, 2022). Hence, their training starts with beats and body movements before acting.

Figure 5: Keremane Shivananda Hegde's *Dakshayajna* (2023)

(Courtesy: Hegde, K. S. (2023). *Dakshayajna*.

<https://nsd.gov.in/delhi/index.php/dakshayajna-yakshagana/>)

On the other hand, Soma Giri's "Silence" (2023) integrates mime, Kalari, and postmodern elements by interlinking with other contemporary dance movements. Following the choreographic work and inspiration of Giri, the focus of the performance is to engage and convey the stage actors' inner feelings and emotions, and the dance and non-verbal body acts portray physicality and psychological themes. The specific difference between the sharply outlined, transit movements of the contemporary theatre and modern dance-theatre acts and the more fluid, personal, and exploratory movements of contemporary dance makes for a dynamic

visual and emotive setting that powerfully underscore the creative approaches that Giri brings to both choreography and drama. In this production, sets are used as the significant visual. Crafts made of bamboo are used to convey symbolic acts and express emotions.

Figure 6: Soma Giri's Silence (2023)

(Courtesy: Giri, S. (2023).

Silence. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=w1h9e7fADEw>)

Choreographies

In Kavalam Narayana Panikkar's "Karimkutty" (2020), traditional Indian dance movements are employed to depict the cultural and emotional crux of the storyline. The choreography is traditional, but the dancing is tailored to fit into the play, while the structure of the dance is traditional. The use of classical dance movements in the choreography of the production gives the show a culturally rich and realistic feel, which also helps to make the performance more dramatic and powerful. This production uses live orchestras, traditional musical instruments, and folk dance movements in great detail. Costumes inspired by folk culture and the use of vibrant drapery make the performance folk-centric.

On the other hand, Shilpika Bordoloi's "A Human Endeavour" (2020) has a combination of modern elements derived from Indian traditional dance forms. She is a dancer-choreographer and practices physical theatre. Her training in Manipuri (Classical Indian Dance), Martial Arts, and Modern Choreography training by Daksha Seth, A Modern Dancer and choreographer from Kerala, is visible in her production's scenography and body vocabulary. Bordoloi's choreography is more flexible and investigates, the body's possibilities, gestures, and dynamics of movement. The combination of modern and classical movements in dance provides

a broad and diverse vocabulary for expression that enables Bordoloi to address issues of individuality, people, and culture.

Figure 7: Shilpika Bordoloi's *A Human Endeavour* (2020)

(Courtesy: Bordoloi, S. (2020). *A Human Endeavour*.
<https://sangeetnatak.gov.in/photogallery/29>)

Production Settings

The choreography of these dance dramas is carefully crafted in order to reveal the narrative and the themes that are present in them. This is evident in the “Live Nukes!” (2020) directed by Kevin Duvall and Taylor Brewerton, where the movements instilled in the physical theatre and the contemporary body twists are supported by the use of a simple stage design that enhances the physical appearance of the actors. Albeit an empty stage, the audience is able to focus solely on the physicality of the acting, an intensity of emotion that is portrayed in the movement of the actors. This physical theatre performance targets mature audiences, as the subject portrayed requires the audience's own perspective and understanding.

Figure 8: Kevin Duvall and Taylor Brewerton’s *Live Nukes!* (2020)
(Courtesy: Duvall, K., & Brewerton, T. (2020). *Live Nukes!*
<https://vimeo.com/159406053>)

In contrast, Goutam’s “*Moimonsingha Ge Itika*” (2019) also includes folk dance, but it is presented in a more elaborate set design that represents the culture and locale of the story. Director Goutam trained in Kathak, Bharatanatyam, and classical Vocal Music, and is an acting trainer as well. The traditional props, costumes, and set designs help to bring the action on the stage to rural India, which helps to draw the audience into the performance and make them feel it is more natural and connected to Indian culture. The ballads of *Moimonsingha Geetika* show a society where women are the heads of the family, and the woman gets to choose her husband. *Mahua* from the play is the essence of womanhood in the Bengal’s folk literature.

Figure 9: Goutam's Moimonsingha Ge Itika (2019)

(Courtesy: Goutam. (2019). Moimonsingha Geetika.

<https://20brm.nsd.gov.in/moimonsingha-geetika/>)

Thematic Exploration

The concepts depicted in these dance dramas range from the choreographical methods and directorial strategies employed in the productions. In the contemporary piece “Loose Woman,” choreographed by Maya K. Rao in 2020, the dancers incorporate contemporary movements and slow body movements to discuss the issues of gender and identity and the norms society imposes upon individuals. Thus, Rao’s choreography and direction critique the patriarchal norms and gender stereotyping, and utilising the body as a form of protest and liberation. Rao is trained in Kathakali; she is a performer, director, trainer, and professor of theatre. May Rao’s Vachika Abhinaya is significantly seen in her every performance. The use of technology, such as a projector-camera, is part of her production’s technicality. Having performed in several Bharat Ranga Mahotsav, she is regarded as a women’s solo, creative theatre performer.

Figure 10: Maya K. Rao's *Loose Woman* (2020)

(Courtesy: Rao, M. K. (2020). *Loose Woman*.
<https://www.thehindu.com/entertainment/dance/maya->

In Jayachandran Palazhy's "*Bhinna Vinyasa*" (2018), elements of modernity are employed in performing sections that address themes of division and merger. He is a renowned modern dancer and choreographer in India and the director of Attakalari, a premier institute for modern dance and choreography in Bengaluru. Palazhy's choreography focuses on the body's continuous movement and its elements as if the body is one, raising philosophical and existential questions. This work can be described as an abstract piece with a non-linear plot and multimedia elements, which requires the audience to grasp for meaning and interpret the meaning behind movements.

Figure 11: Jayachandran Palazhy's *Bhinna Vinyasa* (2018)

(Courtesy: Palazhy, J. (2018). *Bhinna Vinyasa*. <https://fabbricaeuropa.net/en/attakalari-repertory-company-bangalorebhinna-vinyasa/>)

Impactand Significance

Though it is impossible to draw all analysis and writings of all 72 dance-theatre performances in this research paper, it sheds light on understanding the new waves of creativity with the convergence of Indianness. Incorporating dance and drama in these productions has revolutionized Indian theatre and opened new horizons for creativity. The Bharat Ranga Mahotsav has helped to facilitate this intercultural interaction and has encouraged the generation and performance of new and experimental works that combine elements of dance and theatre. Some directors like Keremane Shivananda Hegde, Soma Giri, and Kavalam Narayana Panikkar have depicted how traditional dances can be presented in a modified way, and that is relevant to modern society. Their work can be perceived as a reflection of cultural values and simultaneously shows that there is always room for novelties and imagination. Therefore, choreographers like Shilpika Bordoloi, Jayachandran Palazy, Navtej Singh Johar, Sangeeta Sharma, Bharat Sharma, Padmini Chettur, and Maya K. Rao have experimented with the dance and incorporated it as a means of conveying narratives and voicing opinions. Their choreography shows how the human body can express itself and convey different emotions and meanings.

Case of BRM'S Dance-Theatre

Out of 72 Dance-Theatre productions performed in the BRM till 2023, 16 were staged by the Non-Indian (western and eastern) participant groups, choreographers, and theatre directors. The story, body movement, vocabulary impact, and adaption of their respective country's culture are visible in these performances—one thing particularly noticeable in Western contemporary performance, whether dance or theatre, is technicality. Today, access to technology, innovation and solutions is much easily shared across the globe, such as light technology, theatre automation, mechanical equipment, and customization. And these things hardly impressed us as an Indian audience. Like Uday Shankar's initial stage props, which were highly mechanical, Indian audiences found these something new. However, what makes us astonished is the creative effects within the known technicality. Unlike a mime theatre form, in

contemporary dance creations, non-verbal performances are usually staged with thematic music and sound effects. In 2018, the Theatre Olympics was hosted by the National School of Drama, and the Highest number of international participations were recorded. According to the data from NSD, 160 plays were staged in different cities in India, of which 17 were dance-drama productions, and the rest 143 were general theatrical productions.

Furthermore, out of 17, 5 international groups took part and performed their dance theatre. These plays/productions were *Almost Alive*, directed and choreographed by Sabine Molenaar, and were non-verbal play. *Made in Ilva* by Anna Dora Dorno was in English, *Pyramus & This* by written and directed by Jehan Aloysius, also was in English; *The Restaurant of Many Orders*, written and directed by Hiroshi Koike, was multilingual. *Sakura* by Kevin Yoshimura was written in Japanese. Whoever performed, directed, or choreographed dance-drama or dance-theatre in BRM, their training background shows they are trained dancers. Even directors with theatre training backgrounds made such plays in collaboration with trained dancers and choreographers. Hence, it shows that to create dance-drama plays, the director must understand the movement vocabulary of any particular dance and must be trained in any dance form, with knowledge or exposure to contemporary dance. Theatre directors can produce a play in collaboration with different artists with different training and art backgrounds, whereas a trained and aspiring dancer are often seen as an individual performer, choreographer, and producer of their dance or solo and duet dance-drama production.

In 2000, one year after BRM was founded, Bharat Sharma, a contemporary choreographer, performer, and son of modern-contemporary dancer, Uday Shanker's student, Narendra Sharma, was the first artist to perform contemporary dance ballet. In the Indian context, it is visible that the choreographer and performer of dance, dance-drama have an Indian classical dance training background; later, they turned to contemporary practitioners in the shadow of creativity in dance. As Anita Ratnam stated, "In India, the word 'contemporary' applies to anyone who wants to move away from their guru or the

tradition they have learned, to experiment and explore” (as cited in Leday, 2019).

Conclusion

The critical observation of the dance-drama productions presented during Bharat Ranga Mahotsav highlights the varied and novel aspects of Indian theatre. These two forms of performances have helped enhance the arts culture and break the barriers that come with traditional performances. The festival has played an important role in promoting this creative interaction, where directors, choreographers, and performers can experiment. These works of directors like Keremane Shivananda Hegde, Soma Giri, Shanti Bardhan, Santosh Nair, and Kavalam Narayana Panikkar represent how cultural heritages remain essential and how they can be explored further in theatre through the body movements adapted from Indian culture. Their work shows how it is possible to maintain cultural integrity and still be relevant to the present society and its issues. Shilpika Bordoloi, Sangeeta Sharma, Bharat Sharma, Narendra Sharma, Nimmy Raphel, Maya K. Rao etc., have displayed how their training in dance can be employed as a medium for storytelling in theatre and presenting the world as it is, thus expanding the possibilities of conventional performance and the role of dance.

Therefore, as Indian theatre progresses, it is expected that dance and drama will be part of it for the foreseeable future. Further studies could also examine how intercultural productions affect the current trends in theatre and its contribution to cultural conservation. Further investigation of the dance-drama encounters will undoubtedly help enhance the richness and variety of Indian theatre and dance and maintain its significance in the future. The Bharat Ranga Mahotsav will therefore continue to contribute to this process and encourage new trends and experiments in the performing arts.

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End Notes

1. The concept 'Theatre of Roots' was developed in the postcolonial time during 1960s-1970s to create a synthesis between the Western theatre practices and the Indian tradition. It was also to develop a kind of hybrid theatre out of the amalgamation of the two different cultures: East and West which was followed by most of the theatre practitioners as a nationalistic theatre movement.
2. Natya means "drama." Drama is when a person plays the role of a specific character and imitates the character perfectly in every way possible, including walking, talking, and dressing, to generate an impression on the audience as if the actor is the character.

Natya consists of three components: Nritta (pure dance), Nritya (communicative body language), and Naataka (dramatic storytelling). The Dionysus Festival is a central event of theatrical performances. Often known as the "Greater Dionysia," it was Athens' annual theatrical event in the fifth century.
3. Abhinaya refers to the technique of representation, which is used to communicate the message of the play and elicit emotion (rasa). According to the *Namyauâstra* (a treatise on drama). Abhinaya (representation methods) are divided into four categories: *angika* (physical), *vacika* (vocal), *aharya* (costumes and make-up), and *sattvika* (temperament).
4. Bharata or Bharat Muni is the author of the *Natyashastra*, an Indian treatise that discusses and analyses all aspects of the performing arts.
5. Natya is a Sanskrit word that means drama. Drama is when a person plays the role of a specific character and imitates the character in every way possible, including walking, talking, and dressing, to generate an impression on the audience as if the actor is the character.
6. Nritya is a blend of Natya (a drama) and Nritta (a pure dance without expression or acting). Nritya consists of acting, expression, body movement, hand gestures, and footwork based on rhythm. Nritya (dance) is performed with expressiveness and rhythmic translation based on a song.
7. Maya Krishna Rao is an Indian theater performer, stand-up comedian, and social activist. Recipient of the Sangeet Natak Akademi Award.

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